

Orthopteran (insect) diversity from Haveli and Maval Tahasil of the Pune District, Maharashtra, India

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ABSTRACT

In the present paper 20 species belonging to 5 superfamilies, 5 families and 15 subfamilies and 20 genera are reported. The study was carried out between June 2011 to April 2012 in Haveli and Maval tahasil of Pune district, Maharashtra, India. The order Orthoptera is divided in to two suborder viz Caelifera and Ensifera. The suborder Caelifera includes short horned grasshopper, locust and grouse locust however, Ensifera includes longhorned grasshopper, katydids, cricket and mole cricket.

Key words:- Haveli, Maval, Biodiversity.

INTRODUCTION

The number of known species of Orthoptera from the world is about 20,000 out of this India support 1, 750 species (Tandon and Hazra, 1998) i.e about 10% are known from India. Most of the species are tropical but are also well represented in temperate areas. They are found from sea level to the high altitude in Himalaya (Bhowmik & Rui, 1982; Mehta *et al.*, 2002 and Shishodia *et al.*, 2002).

The member of the order Orthoptera includes jumping insects like grasshoppers, katydids, grouse locust, tree cricket, cricket and mole cricket. Orthopteran insects functionally important being the dominant above grouped invertebrates in rangeland when by biomass (Scott *et al.*, 1979; Risser *et al.*, 1981). They are therefore forming the good study subject for

research on prediction models from an ecological perspective grasshoppers are functionally the dominant herbivorous consume foliage and it is an important insect group in grassland ecosystem and playing an important role in supporting population dynamic theory (Odum *et al.*, 1962 and Van Hook 1971).

In diversity study making investigation of species is of prime importance because assessment of biodiversity loss of prime importance because assessment of biodiversity loss is base on it and will help to formulate conservation strategies for their sustainable utilization.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The selected tahasil Haveli and Maval of Pune district are situated at 19.0⁰ North latitude and 73.15⁰ East longitude. The area has contour interval 100 meter maximum height from the

Figure-1. The map of study site: tahasil Haveli and Maval of Pune District, Maharashtra

mean sea level is 1200 meters and minimum height 300 meters above mean sea level. The major rivers flowing through area are Indrayani, Mula, Mutha, Andhra, Kundali, Pavana and the major lakes are Pavana, Andhra, Khadkwasla, Pashan, Katraj, Shiravate Kalvan and Gibbs lake.

The total forest in Maval Tahshil is 205.099 sq. km. and the total forest in Haveli Tahshil in 112.91 sq. km. The major forest in the Maval tahshil is in the region of Lonavala, Pavana lake, Gibbs lake and Major forest in Haveli tahasil in the region of Katraj, Sinhagad and surrounding region. The total forest in two tahasil in 318.01 sq. km. The study region in characterized by tropical semi evergreen forest, dry deciduous area & scrub region.

Sampling of grasshopper was done during June 2011 to April 2012 by using sweep net. Samples collections took place from 10am to 6pm. The individuals were identified in the laboratory using identification Keys (Kirby, 11914; Chopard, 1969).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In the present study, 20 species of Orthopteran insets belonging to 20 genera, 15 subfamilies and 5 families were reported. Among Orthoptera order short horned grasshopper belonging to family Acrididae are dominant with 13 species, second dominant family is Tettigoniidae with 3 species. Third Gryllidae with 2 species while family Pygrogmoridae and family Tetrigidae represented by 1 species each.

Grassland ecosystem supported 70% of the grasshoppers, 12 belonging to Acrididae and 2 belonging to Tettigoniidae. Dry land ecosystem supported 20% of the grasshoppers 1 belonging to Acrididae, 1 with Pyrgomorphidae, 2 with Gryllidae. Dam ecosystem represented 5% i.e 1 species belonging to family Tetrigidae and forest ecosystem represented by 5% i.e 1 species belonging to family Tettigoniidae.

In a study Senthilkumar *et al.*, (2006) have recorded 25 species Orthoptera under 4 families from Gibbon wildlife sanctuary Assam. Shishodia and Gupta (2009) have recorded 165 species under 16 families in Himachal Pradesh. Pranjape (1994) have recorded 16 species of Tetrigidae in Maharashtra.

In the present study 8 subfamilies of Acrididae have been recorded in diverse habitat. Grasses were found to be the most common habitats for grasshoppers.

SYSTEMATIC ACCOUNT

Order: Orthoptera

Superfamily: Acrididoidea

Family: Acrididae

Subfamily: Truxalinae

Truxalis indica Bolivar, 1902

Subfamily: Acridinae

Acrida exaltata Walker, 1859

Phlaeoba antennata Brunner

Subfamily: Oedipodinae

Gastimargus africanus africanus Saussure, 1888

Trilophidia annulata Thunberg, 1815

Aiolopus thalassinus tamulus Fabricius, 1798

Subfamily: Hemiacridinae

Hieroglyphus banian Fabricius, 1798

Subfamily: Oxyinae

Oxya hyla hyla Serville, 1831

Subfamily: Cyrtacanthacridinae

Patanga succincta Johanson, 1763

Subfamily: Catantopinae

Catantops pinguis innotabilis Walker, 1870

Xenocatantops humilis humilis Serville, 1839

Stenocatantops splendens Thunberg, 1815

Subfamily: Eyprepnemiinae

Tylotropidius varicornis Walker, 1870

Superfamily: Pyrgomorpoidea

Family: Pyrgomorphidae

Subfamily: Pyrgomorphinae

Chrotogonus trachypterus trachypterus

Bianchard, 1836

Superfamily: Tetrigoidea

Family: Tetrigidae

Subfamily: Scelimeninae

Eucrietettix flavopictus, Bolivar, 1902

Suborder: Ensifera

Superfamily: Grylloidea

Family: Gryllidae

Subfamily: Gryllinae

Modicogryllus (Modicogryllus) confirmatus

Walker, 1859

Teleogryllus occipitalis occipitalis Serville, 1838

Superfamily: Tettigonioidae

Family: Tettigoniidae

Subfamily: Phaneropterinae

Phaneroptera sp.

Subfamily: Mecopodinae

Mecopoda elongate Linnaeus, 1758

Subfamily: Conocephalinae

Conocephalus (Anisoptera) maculates Le

Guillou, 1841

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